

The Lithic Assemblages of Jbel Irhoud

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ملخص

سنتطرق من خلال هذه المقالة لدراسة الأدوات الحجرية المكتشفة في إطار برنامج البحث الخاص بجبل إيغود والذي انطلق العمل به منذ سنة 2004. من أهم ملاحظات هذه الدراسة هو التشابه بين الأدوات المكتشفة و تلك التي تم استخراجها سابقا من هذا الموقع. ونظرا لقلّة النواة والشظايا و كثرة الأدوات الحجرية المكتملة الصنع. و على رأسها الكاشطات. فان المجموعة الحجرية الخاصة بموقع جبل إيغود تدل على استعمالات جد خاصة وعلى تطوير إنسان إيغود لأدواته. ولعل الأعمال الجارية حاليا بالموقع ستفضي إلى المزيد من التوضيح بهذا الصدد.

Abstract

Here we review the lithic assemblages previously described from the site and follow this with a brief update on the main characteristics of our recently excavated assemblage. Together the various collections from Irhoud give a very consistent picture. Though there are very few cores in any of the collections, the flakes show a high proportion of Levallois blank production. The proportion of tools is very high, even in the controlled samples coming from the Tixier excavations and our current excavations. Among the tools, scrapers are most numerous, and of these simple and pointed forms dominate. Characteristic of the tools as well are off-axis points or so-called déjeté scrapers. Given the low frequency of both cores and debris and given the high frequency of retouched tools, the Irhoud assemblages suggest a fairly specific use of the site. Work is still underway to better understand the behavioral context of these assemblages.

Introduction

The Moroccan site of Jbel Irhoud is best known for its fossil hominins. Starting in 1961, work at the site has produced an important number of taxonomically diagnostic fossils, including three partially preserved crania and two well preserved mandibles, that now demonstrate that archaic members of our species were present in northwest Africa by 300 ka and very likely present as well across large portions of Africa by this time⁵. This latter point relies heavily on the fact that the Irhoud fossils are associated with Middle Stone Age artifacts, and the Middle Stone Age dates to roughly this age in east⁶ and south Africa⁷. That the Irhoud fossils were associated with stone tools and fauna and that these stone tools had affinities with the European Middle Paleolithic or Mousterian was noted from the initial work by Ennouchi in the first part of the 1960s⁸. Today we call these assemblages Middle Stone Age, but their character is unchanged. Levallois is the primary technology of blank production, and the retouched component is dominated by scrapers but also especially pointed forms. There is no evidence for large cutting tools, and there is no evidence for the type fossils (e.g. tanged artifacts) of the later Aterian.

Here we briefly overview previous work on the Jbel Irhoud lithics, and we follow this with an

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⁵. Ennouchi E. 1962 ; Ennouchi E. 1966a ; Ennouchi E. 1966b ; Ennouchi E. 1968 ; Hublin J.-J. *et al.* 2017 ; Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

⁶. Sahle M. *et al.* 2014 ; Brooks A. S. *et al.* 2018.

⁷. Porat N. *et al.* 2010.

⁸. Ennouchi E. 1963 ; Balout L. 1970.

update to our last publication of the lithics⁹. This update includes additional data from the 2012 season and data from the 2017 season of excavation. While this report supercedes the previous publication¹⁰, it should nevertheless be considered preliminary as additional excavation work at the site is planned for 2018.

Fig. 1. On-going excavations at the site of Jbel Irhoud in 2017. The area covered under the green tarp is where most of the excavation prior to 2017 took place and where the new fossils hominins were discovered. The area to the right, where one person is seen working, roughly corresponds to the area excavated by Tixier in 1967 and 1969. Though the full extent of Ennouchi's excavation is unclear, most of his work probably took place in front and to the left of current excavations.

The Ennouchi and Tixier collections

There are in fact several Irhoud collections, and these have been studied and published by various authors. First, Ennouchi first noted the presence of stone tools in 1963 in association with the second fossil cranium, and he described them (based on observations by Balout) as Levallois Mousterian. This initial sample of 40 pieces was subsequently commented upon by Balout (1970) where also he was able to report an additional 400 artifacts collected by the workmen and during visits by Ennouchi. Balout describes this assemblage again as Levallois Mousterian and emphasizes that there is absolutely no evidence for Aterian elements. Instead the assemblage is dominated by Mousterian scrapers, and he notes the presence of *déjeté* scrapers. Interesting too is the complete absence of cores, though he does note some Levallois preparation flakes, and the relatively low frequency of flake debris. Finally, he also notes the presence of heated flakes in this assemblage.

⁹. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

¹⁰. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

Next, Tixier accompanied by de Bayle des Hermens conducted two seasons of excavation at the site in 1967 and 1969¹¹. These excavations are notable because they covered the entire sequence as it was known then and because they employed standard methodologies of the day, including point proveniencing. Unfortunately, Tixier did not produce a complete study of these excavations ; however, he did publish some observations of the excavation, including a section drawing, in his report of the lithic material associated with the human humerus coming from Layer 18 of these excavations¹². He reports on an assemblage of 217 artifacts (not including debris) of which nearly half consists of retouched tools (echoing a point made earlier by Balout on the high tool to flake ratio). Like Balout, Tixier concludes that in a European framework the assemblage is best described as a Levallois Mousterian or, following Bordes' classification system, a Typical Mousterian of Levallois type rich in scrapers. Tixier also notes in his sample the frequent presence of déjeté scrapers and the lack of cores, and he emphasizes the complete absence of Aterian elements of any kind. Both Balout and Tixier note that in their collections there is some variability in raw materials and differences in how they are treated. Higher quality materials, in this case flint, appears to have been primarily worked off site with finished tools being discarded on site, while lower quality raw materials, like quartzite, appear to have been worked on site and were used less frequently for tool production.

Then in 1995, Salih published on the Irhoud lithics using a third collection from the site. His sample consisted of an additional 1600 artifacts discovered in storage in Rabat, Morocco, and previously thought to have been exported or lost. This much larger sample from the site further amplifies the main characteristics previous described. Most of the tools are on flint while most of the flake debris is on quartzite¹³. Cores continue to be rare in this sample, and likewise suggest to Salih that flint artifacts were imported into the site already prepared. In the flake debris, Levallois technology is frequent, and platforms frequently show faceting. The frequency of tools is again high in this sample at roughly 40%, and of the tools are dominated by scrapers including again a large portion of pointed forms. Of the pointed forms, again, déjeté scrapers are quite frequent. Once again, even with this greatly expanded sample, Salih finds no evidence for either large cutting tool technologies or Aterian elements.

Taken together these three studies make a sample of just over 2200 stone artifacts from Jbel Irhoud and produce a very consistent result. Though it is difficult to know exactly where Ennouchi made his collection, we do know that he removed the bulk of the sediments from the site, and we know that Tixier worked on adjacent deposits left by Ennouchi and that he covered the whole sequence. These points together suggest that the sequence contains very little variability both horizontally and vertically. This latter point was emphasized by Tixier¹⁴ who reported details on Layer 18 only but considered them characteristic of the entire sequence. In each of the previous Irhoud samples, the frequency of tools is quite high. It is not unusual for tool frequencies to be elevated in unsystematic collections (i.e. the Ennouchi collections), but in this case this point is confirmed in the systematic and controlled collection coming from Tixier's excavations. For all of the authors, the collection fits well within a European Mousterian framework with especially its emphasis on scrapers. The retention of the term Mousterian to describe these assemblages, rather than Middle Stone Age, is likely to a large extent historical¹⁵, and both Salih and Tixier are careful to note the European context of their comparisons and both also find similarities between Irhoud and other north African assemblages. Nevertheless, the assemblage does indeed look Mousterian. Still, What makes Irhoud Middle Stone Age is the strong emphasis on points in addition to the prepared core techno-

¹¹. Hublin J.-J., Tillier A.-M. and Tixier J. 1987.

¹². Hublin J.-J., Tillier A.-M. and Tixier J. 1987.

¹³. Salih A. 1995.

¹⁴. Hublin J.-J., Tillier A.-M. and Tixier J. 1987.

¹⁵. Garcea E. a. A. 2012

logy, but here is where the distinction between whether a tool is a convergent scraper or a point becomes important. On the one hand, Irhoud looks like a short-term, task specific site (logistical mobility) where finished tools, including hunting weaponry, are brought into the site, maintained and, as a result, occasionally discarded. On the other hand, Irhoud fits models of raw material conservation and resharpening reduction where single scrapers are transformed into double and then into convergent forms before being discarded (Dibble 1995). Assessing which of these models is more likely is one of the research foci for the new excavations. However, based on the previous work, there are two points to mention in favor of the intentional production of pointed forms. First, normally in a scraper reduction model the proportion of discarded scrapers of single, double, and convergent types should progress incrementally from one to the other. To the contrary, the Irhoud assemblages are dominated by single and convergent forms with far fewer double scrapers (Fig. 2). This bimodal pattern is not consistent with scraper reduction and suggests instead some mixture of the two models wherein the number of pointed forms is a result of both reduction processes and the deliberate production of pointed forms. Second, consistent with this idea, in Salih's publication of 1600 artifacts, one bifacial point is illustrated¹⁶. Small bifacial points such as these are rare to completely absent in Mousterian assemblages but, to the contrary, are quite common in Middle Stone Age assemblages¹⁷, including in quite old Middle Stone Age assemblages¹⁸.

Adding to the previous collections

Since 2004, new work at the site has produced additional lithic material from the complete sequence (Table 1). As described in Richter et al., the new excavations are immediately adjacent to the areas excavated by Tixier. By excavating a portion of Tixier's section that was still preserve and with the help of some nails in his section, we were able to approximately link our excavations to his. This said, however, we established our own stratigraphic sequence of 7 main layers (1-7 from top to bottom) rather than try to follow Tixier's sequence of 22 stratigraphic units. In our sequence, there are stone artifacts from the base (Layer 7) up through Layer 4, and nearly all of the hominin fossils come from Layer 7.

Table 1. Artifact inventory for the new Jbel Irhoud excavations with volume excavated and densities.

Layer	Liters	Bones	Lithics	Bone Density	Lithic Density
1	434.0	0	0	0.00	0.00
2	455.0	0	0	0.00	0.00
3	644.0	1	0	0.00	0.00
4	4249.0	117	27	0.03	0.01
5	1045.5	174	95	0.17	0.09
6	1532.0	238	186	0.16	0.12
7	1860.5	523	272	0.28	0.15
A	2129.0	394	44	0.19	0.02
B	1620.0	478	33	0.30	0.02

¹⁶. Salih A. 1995 : fig. 2, number 6.

¹⁷. Brooks A. S. *et al.* 2006.

¹⁸. Sahle M. *et al.* 2014.

Fig. 2. A comparison of single, double and pointed scraper types from the Salih (1995) and from the Tixier collection (Hublin, Tillier, and Tixier 1987). Mousterian points, convergent scrapers and déjeté scrapers are included in pointed forms. Transverse scrapers are included in single scrapers. Limace (N=4) are ignored.

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Though this report is preliminary because there is still more excavation to be conducted at the site, the numbers presented here include all of the material excavated to date and thus vary somewhere from what was previously reported by Richter D. *et al.*¹⁹. The basic character of the industry, however, has not changed.

First, a few taphonomic observations can be made. As noted in Richter *et al.*²⁰, the percentage of heated lithics (34.62%) is quite high in the assemblage. The percentage of heated lithics also varies little between layers (Table 2). Second, breakage rates and the frequency of edge damage are reported in Tables 3 and 4. Edge damage was recorded following the methods described in Mc Pherron S. *et al.*²¹ and Goldberg *et al.*²². The numbers are at the low end of the range seen in layers with relatively few post-depositional alterations other than trampling²³. Breakage is computed as the percentage of complete flakes in the sample of complete and proximal flakes. Only non-heated artifacts are considered here because it is known that heating increases breakage rates²⁴. As result, because heating is quite high in these assemblage, the sample sizes are low, but the numbers are well with the range of comparative data from context with few post-depositional issues²⁵.

<i>Table 2. The percentage of heated lithics by layer.</i>			<i>Table 3. The percentage of complete flakes by layer.</i>		
Layer	N	Percent Heated	Layer	N	Percent Complete
4	13	38.5	4	4	75.0
5	45	37.8	5	12	83.3
6	107	31.8	6	45	73.3
7	121	35.5	7	44	75.0

Table 4. The percentage of edge damage categories by layer. 1-Face indicates damage on either the interior or exterior face. 2-Faces indicates damage on both faces. There were no rolled artifacts in the assemblages.

¹⁹. Richter D. *et al.* 2017 : Tables 2-4.

²⁰. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

²¹. Mc Pherron S. *et al.* 2014.

²². Goldberg P. *et al.* 2018.

²³. Goldberg P. *et al.* 2018.

²⁴. Goldberg P. *et al.* 2018.

²⁵. Goldberg P. *et al.* 2018.

Layer	N	None	1-Face	2-Faces
4	19	52.6	36.8	10.5
5	77	68.8	15.6	15.6
6	163	63.8	24.5	11.7
7	225	63.6	26.7	9.8

One of the striking aspects of the assemblage remains the high frequency of tools. There are only 2.7 flakes (with platforms) for each retouched tool (with a platform). There are some cores. Thus far 11 cores have been excavated. Of the retouched artifacts, 28.7% are made on Levallois blanks. Of the unretouched artifacts, 21.2% are Levallois. Only four blanks (retouched or not) could be classified as coming from a blade technology, 39 artifacts have a blade form, and the length:width ratio for the complete, unretouched flakes is 1.57. Platforms are mostly plain (54.7%) followed by faceted (20.2%), dihedral (17.1%), and cortical (4.1%). Of the retouched artifacts, 77.5% are scrapers. Of the scrapers, simple (44.5%) and convergent (29.1% including Mousterian points and déjeté scrapers) forms dominate. Déjeté scrapers are 6.4% of the scrapers. The frequency of double scrapers is 13.6%, and transverse forms are rare (4.5%). There are only two Upper Paleolithic retouched types (piercers) and no pedunculated artifacts. There are 4 truncated-faceted artifacts. There are no clear differences or trends in the assemblages of Layers 4, 5, 6, and 7, though small sample sizes make comparisons difficult.

Table 5. Summary of artifact types.

	4	5	6	7	Totals
Convergent Scraper	1	4	6	7	18
Déjetés Scraper	0	0	3	4	7
Double Scraper	0	4	4	7	15
Miscellaneous	0	0	1	0	1
Notched	0	5	5	14	24
Other Scrapers	0	0	4	4	8
Piercer	0	0	1	1	2
Retouched Point	0	3	3	3	9
Simple Scraper	3	8	13	25	49
Transverse Scraper	1	0	3	1	5
Truncated-faceted	1	0	1	2	4
Core	2	0	4	5	11
Platform Flake	1	14	24	41	80
Flake Debris	11	42	108	134	295
Shatter	1	6	7	13	27
Totals	21	86	187	261	555

Table 6. Summary of platform types.

	4	5	6	7	Totals
Cortical	0	2	5	8	15
Dihedral	4	9	20	29	62
Faceted	0	6	27	40	73
Other	0	0	0	2	2
Plain	9	35	70	84	198
Punctiform	0	2	5	5	12
Removed	0	2	3	0	5
Totals	13	56	130	168	367

Table 7. Summary of blank technology.

	4	5	6	7	Totals
Retouch	0	1	1	2	4
Blade	0	0	2	2	4
Clactonian	0	0	0	1	1
Discooidal	0	0	0	1	1
Levallois	3	19	29	50	101
Normal	10	50	119	147	326
Totals	13	70	151	203	437

Discussion and Conclusions

Based on our assemblages, we too would characterized Jbel Irhoud as Levallois Mousterian in a European framework. The percentage of scrapers (essential count) is actually high enough that a Ferrassie type Mousterian denomination would be warranted. This is true as well when considering just Layer 7 (73.5%), which is the equivalent of Tixier's Layer 18. However, as others have suggested already²⁶, despite the historical tradition of using the term Mousterian to describe North Africa assemblages, we prefer to place the Jbel Irhoud assemblages in an African, Middle Stone Age framework. Additionally, like all of the others before us working on in total a much larger collection of material, we found absolutely no trace of the Aterian facies of the Middle Stone Age.

²⁶. Garcea E. a. A. 2012 ; Dibble H. *et al.* 2013.

Fig. 3. Flint artefacts from layers 6 and 7. a–e, Convergent scrapers (layer 6). f, g, Levallois flakes (layer 6). h, Transverse scraper (layer 6). i, Limace (layer 6). j, Déjeté scraper (layer 7). k, Levallois flake (layer 7). l, Convergent scraper (layer 7). m, Convergent scraper (layer 7). n, Unifacial point (layer 7). o, Levallois flake (layer 7). Outlines represent profile views. Reprinted from Richter *et al.*²⁷.

²⁷. Richter D. *et al.* 2017

Fig. 4. Flint artefacts. a, b, e, Unifacial points (layer 6). c, d, Convergent scrapers (layer 6). f, Déjeté scraper (layer 6). g, h, Convergent scrapers (layer 7). i, Unifacial point (layer 7). j, Levallois Flake (layer 7). k, m, Double scrapers (layer 7). l, Déjeté scraper (layer 7).

Fig. 5. Stone artefacts from layer 7. a, b, Quartz flakes. c, m, Flint Levallois flakes. d, i, Silicified limestone flakes. e, g, h, Flint flakes with some edge damage. f, Flint flake. j, n, Silicified limestone flakes with some edge damage. k, l, Flint Levallois flakes with some edge damage. Reprinted from Richter D. *et al.*²⁹.

²⁸. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

²⁹. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

Our assemblage also confirms the observations made previously that there is a strikingly high percentage of retouched tools, especially for those made on flint, and a general low frequency of debris. This is significant because at least in our case the sample comes from a controlled collection where all of the deposits were screened. Though the data are not presented here, this trend continues in the small finds coming the screens (the 5-25 mm fraction). Normally this could indicate a site formation issue such as the removal of the small fraction by water run-off. At Irhoud there are no geological observations to support this idea, and so it seems that very little on-site blank production and tool manufacture/maintenance took place.

Additionally, in terms of site formation processes, edge damage and breakage data suggest no major taphonomic issues. However, there is substantial evidence for fire in the deposits (an observation confirmed by the presence of fire features, see Richter *et al.*³⁰). The percentage of heated flints is higher than most assemblages with published data from southwest France Middle Paleolithic³¹ and similar to the higher percentages published for Tabun³². What these data suggest is that the area currently under excavation and the area previously excavated by Tixier (where also fire features were recorded (see Hublin J.-J. *et al.*³³ corresponds to a central portion of the site where fires were made and stone tools discarded).

Thus Jbel Irhoud is a Middle Stone Age site with Levallois technology and a strong emphasis on scraper production. Pointed forms are well represented, and in particular off axis or déjeté scrapers are characteristic of the assemblages. The raw materials are mostly high quality flint brought to the site likely from some distance. There is relatively little evidence for on-site blank production on this material. Rather, on-site blank production was mainly done on locally available raw materials. Whether the pointed artifacts from Jbel Irhoud can be demonstrated to have been used as points (as opposed to being convergent scrapers) is a subject of on-going research, but it is possible that retouched component of the assemblages represents a combination of these two processes (point manufacture and scraper reduction). This may account for the bimodal distribution of single and convergent scrapers. How these features of the Jbel Irhoud Middle Stone Age assemblages relate to later Middle Stone Age assemblages in the same region³⁴ and to penecontemporaneous Middle Stone Age assemblages elsewhere in Africa is a point worth investigating further, but it is clear from the work thus far completed that Irhoud represents a rather specific site context that is likely structuring much of the variability seen in the assemblages and that needs to be better understood before taking a comparative approach.

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³⁰. Richter D. *et al.* 2017.

³¹. Dibble H. *et al.* 2018.

³². Shimelmitz R. *et al.* 2014.

³³. Hublin J.-J., Tillier A.-M. and Tixier J. 1987.

³⁴. Ramos J. *et al.* 2008.

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